

COVID^X

Watch those inspirational talks by Bruno Delepierre and Eivind Segtnan

INSPIRATIONAL TALKS Bruno Delepierre & Eivind Segtnan

Bruno Delepierre, CEO at Happonomy

Eivind Segtnan, CEO at Synaptic

Bruno Delepierre, CEO at Happonomy, is an entrepreneurial soul, an avid fan of unleashing ideas that can change the world for the better. **Eivind Segtnan**, CEO at SYNAPTIC, started his development in the officer school within the Norwegian army's long-range operations. In addition to being a philanthropist, he managed to build a school in Africa with minimal funding. And Today, more than 5000 children have learned to read and write because of him. Don't miss the opportunity to watch what they said to **inspire the audience!**

[Watch the videos](#)

Save the date for the final Brussels event (21-22 Sept)

You will find networking opportunities, inspirational talks, exhibition of more than 40 healthcare solutions, roundtables

Watch the OC1 Game Changers' videos

Don't miss the Open Call #1 Game Changers videos and learn about each solution. See how they can help your hospital to fight the pandemic.

and more.

#BackToAHealthyFutureEvent

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COVID-X has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101016065. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

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